

THE MAIN PROBLEMS OF LINGUODIDACTICS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK GRAMMAR SYSTEM

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Annotation: The science of linguodidactics develops the general laws of the theory of language teaching, that is, it deals with the methodological basis of language teaching / learning. These include issues such as the goals, content, methods (principles), tools, methods of scientific research, and the relationship of language teaching with other disciplines.

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The grammatical structure of a language is a generally important aspect of its system. Affixes, grammatical suffixes and word formation, syntactic models, word order, auxiliary words and similar grammatical structural elements of languages serve to indicate not only the grammatical or formal meaning, but the exact form of lexical meanings as well. It is important to express these meanings in the translation process. The grammatical forms of different languages rarely match their meaning and function. Interpreters must be able to choose the most appropriate equivalent for each situation. The structure of the translation must match the structure of the original text and the order of the text segments must not change during the translation process. Because it is desirable that each part of the translated text is structurally parallel to the corresponding part of the text in the original language. Generally, it is not possible to find a literal equivalent of one text to another. Translators try to understand the meaning of the original speech as deeply as possible, and then translate the comprehended meaning into the same language as the original. In doing so, he makes effective use of several abovementioned ways, trying to reveal the true meaning of speaker's speech. Nevertheless, it is vastly significant to regard the problems as a concept, and to consider other aspects while analyzing grammatical problems of interpreter training. This will be the subject of the author's further research. Language didactics deals with the teaching and learning of foreign languages in an institutional setting. On the one hand, this concerns the development of foreign language skills (listening, comprehending audio-visual texts, reading, writing and speaking as well as the ability of language mediation); on the other hand, language didactics is about ways of learning and teaching grammar (morphology, syntax) and knowledge of vocabulary (orthography, pronunciation, register, meaning/connotations). Courses in language didactics focus on linguistic phenomena, mechanisms of language learning, character traits of speakers,

desired linguistic competences and the conditions and methods of language classes. The focus of language didactics is influenced by developments in the domain of language research: linguistics, applied linguistics, second language acquisition research, language teaching research and language psychology. It is also informed by current didactic approaches within the branch of foreign language teaching (e.g. competence-orientation, action-orientation, learner-orientation) Language didactics is mostly concerned with issues of institutional foreign language acquisition – a topic in which the other branches of the didactics of foreign languages (literature and culture didactics) also take an interest. This overlap occurs for two reasons: on the one hand, language acquisition cannot take place without the consideration of cultural aspects and on the other hand, literary texts in the foreign language are used in the foreign language classroom to enable learners to get in touch with authentic language. Local theorists and practitioners complain that there are not certain assumptions of methodology of teaching two or more foreign languages at the same time. Although, according to the local curriculum, at linguistic and non-linguistic higher educational establishments in Uzbekistan, students usually learn two foreign languages. All approaches to teaching English and all EFL/ESL teachers, deal one way or another with a teaching of English grammar. As it is defined by the linguists -the words of English and their combinations. The important thing for you to remember is that grammar in an EFL/ESL context is quite different from the grammar you knew and loved (or didn't love) in school. In order to understand a language and express oneself correctly one must assimilate the grammar mechanism of the language studied. Indeed one may know all the words in sentence and yet fail to understand it, if one does not see the relationship between the words in the given sentence. And 'vise' 'versa', a sentence may contain one, two and more unknown words but if one has a good knowledge on the structure of the language one can easily guess the meaning of these words at least find them in a dictionary. However, the word order in these phrases is different: in English phrases, the predicate comes after the subject, whereas in Uzbek phrases, the predicate comes after the subject and object. There are extremely few examples of English and Uzbek speech formulations that are structurally identical. Typically, such expressions have two or three parts: an international telegram – xalqaro telegramma travelers' check – sayohatchilar cheki. Partially discordant categories include tense, voice, and case. There are two cases in English, and six in Uzbek. I heard much about your country – Sizning mamlakatingiz to'g'risida ko'p eshitganman. Two English words —your country are rendered by one Uzbek word —mamlakatingiz. Moreover, they vary from the viewpoint of category of cases. Another example: We are from Tashkent – Biz Toshkentdanmiz. As we see, three English lexemes —are from Tashkent are combined

in one Uzbek lexeme —Toshkentdanmiz. We came here on the invitation of the government of – Biz hukumati taklifiga binoan keldik. In this example the structure of the English expression —on the invitation of government is different by word order in the Uzbek equivalent —hukumati taklifiga (word order is vice versa). As we see in the examples above, set expressions with partial accordance are similar in meaning but differ in structure: one letter – bitta kitob five letters – beshta kitob. As we see, English phrases consist of numeral and noun (singular and plural), but Uzbek phrases consist of numeral and noun in singular. Even in cases of total semantic accordance there may be revealed cases of partial structural discordance: a list of items – molar ro‘yhati (word order differs + Uzbek suffix —i in the word —ro‘yhati) customs restrictions – bojhona cheklovlari (same word order but Uzbek suffix —i in the word —cheklovlaril import license – import uchun ruhsatnoma (same word order + Uzbek postposition —uchun). Total structural discordance is first of all vivid in the category of possession which is expressed by possessive suffixes in Uzbek and by possessive pronouns in English: possessive pronouns in English: May I introduce you to my family? – Sizni oilamga tanishtirishga ruhsat bering. This is your invitation, please. – Marhamat, sizning taklifnomangiz. So, on these common examples we can confirm that a communicant of English-Uzbek conversation should master all possessive pronouns of English and possessive suffixes (endings) of Uzbek.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Shakvat Mirziyoyev. “ It’s time to create a new system of teaching foreign languages – a solid foundation for the future.” 2021
2. Abdulla Avloniy. Òurkiy guliston yoxud axloq. Ò., „O‘qituvchi“, 1992
3. J. Jalolov, Chet til o‘qitish metodikasi „O‘ qituvchi“ Toshkent-2013.
4. Jalolov J.Jahon lingvodidaktikasining zamonaviy konseptual yangilanish bosqich xususida//Horijiy filologiya. №1 (30). – Samarqand, 2009. pp91-95.
5. Джусупов М. Лингводидактика и методика в полинаучной системе языкового образования. //Русский язык за рубежом, 2009, № 2, pp26-32
6. КимВ.Н., КимТ.С. Социальнополитическая терминология–Т., . 2009. С.
7. Lingvodidaktika kak teoritecheskaya osnova obucheniya yazika. Elektronniy resurs: <http://works.doklad.ru/view/NRkF6riOIeo.html>. Data obrasheniya: 03.04.2019.
8. L.Konoplyanik, Interactive methods of teaching foreign languages in higher Education in: Materials of II International Scientific Conference "Modern trends in teaching a second language at schools and institutions of higher education ", Gorlovka, HDPIIM, 2011. - p.p. 84-85.
9. H.Stern, Fundamental Concepts of Language Teaching, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1983.